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Designing a variety selection decision support system for cereal growers

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Abstract

Selecting the correct variety of a cereal crop is a vital first step, influencing all subsequent crop husbandry decisions and determining the potential successfulness of a crop in both economic and agronomic terms. Growers make this decision by considering farm location, local trial results and knowledge, and their priorities. Balancing these factors, information sources, and priorities is challenging for growers. Complex multi-factor analyses are required in the decision-making process; while computer-based decision support systems (DSSs) have been created to support this process, the localized nature and poor user-friendliness of the DSSs have resulted in limited grower adoption. This study aims to design a user-centric DSS to assist growers in selecting an optimal cereal variety for their priorities in each field. The system integrates local factors with independent cereal variety evaluation data, such as national “recommended lists.” It can be applied globally where such listings are available. Two use cases are described with Ireland’s Department of Agriculture, Food, and the Marine and New Zealand’s Foundation for Arable Research wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) recommended lists. Characteristic evaluation scores for each variety were normalized and weighted based on user priorities and field location using the simple additive weighting method. Growers’ local yield history of each variety, if available, can be included to create a site-specific DSS. The outcome is an overall ranking of the varieties present on the recommended list, enabling the user to make an informed decision on their chosen variety while accommodating market demands, seed availability, and their own preference.

Plain Language Summary

A grower needs to decide what variety of a crop to plant before the growing season begins. This decision is very difficult, as it must take many variables into account. This research aims to create a system that helps growers to decide on what variety to plant. It does this by evaluating independent variety trials and taking site-specific

Abbreviations: AHDB, Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board; DAFM, Department of Agriculture, Food, and the Marine; DSS, decision support system; MCDM, multi-criteria decision-making; ML, machine learning; SAW, simple additive weighting; TGW, 1000-grain weight.

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factors such as disease risk and climactic conditions into account. It produces a ranking of varieties that informs the grower of appropriate varieties given their location and the various priorities of the grower.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Before the planting season begins each year, a grower must decide on what variety of a crop they will grow in each individual field. While it might seem intuitive to pick a variety to maximize yield, evidence shows that growers prioritize traits associated with yield stability, such as disease and lodging resistance, over mere yield (Zander et al., 2023), with locally adapted varieties preferred (Macholdt & Honermeier, 2016). Sometimes, a grower will not have a choice, as the market they are aiming for only accepts certain varieties, or there may be a limited choice due to a shortage of certain varieties. However, in most cases, a grower will have a choice to make. To do this, growers will research the varieties available to them and lean on their past experiences with certain varieties in previous growing seasons or the experiences of peers and those whose opinion they value and official recommendations (Macholdt & Honermeier, 2016). The high number of varieties for certain crops and the numerous factors that must be accounted for can transform the process of selecting a cereal variety into a complex, arduous task.

To overcome this issue, numerous variety selection tools have been created to help growers choose a variety that fits their priorities and requirements over the past 40 years, with early versions being database management systems for analyzing varietal field evaluations and to subsequently provide recommendations for specific environments (Martiniello, 1988). These tools use expert systems to overcome the limitations of traditional recommended lists, but farmer uptake remains an issue (McGregor & Thornton, 1990). A web-based system with varietal information was created in Denmark to guide farmers on variety selection. Data are collected from various independent Danish field trial sources, from which users can sort and rank the data according to the displayed varietal characteristics (Jensen, 2001). This work was then expanded on by Detlefsen and Jensen (2004) to create a full decision support system (DSS) for the selection of an appropriate winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) variety for Danish growers. This system focuses on the economics of each variety, considering the expected net revenue and cost of production. There are some limitations with this system as there are many assumptions in the model, such as assuming certain costs are equal for all varieties and utilizing no regional data.

A similar system was created in the United Kingdom for winter wheat, winter barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), and spring barley. The National Institute of Agricultural Botany

Gross Margin Model (Nelson & Meikle, 2001) assesses the gross margin of each variety by totaling the revenue minus variable costs. This deterministic system goes further to provide options to include high-priority diseases and current or expected grain prices. Outcomes are then displayed graphically for simple varietal comparisons. The Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board (AHDB) (2024) developed a variety selection tool based on independent trials it carries out to produce UK recommended lists. This tool is available for wheat, barley, oats (*Avena sativa* L.), and oilseed rape (*Brassica napus* L.). It compares the varietal trial results based on user-chosen characteristics.

As seen in Figure 1, different weightings can be given to different characteristics based upon the priorities of the user and their specific scenario. Regional data are available in addition to soil type data. The tool benefits from access to a comprehensive set of independent trial sites across the United Kingdom. The results are then presented graphically, comparing the yield of each variety to its agronomic performance, which is based upon the selected characteristics and weightings. However, the user must still take their own conclusions and input their own priorities and weightings for this tool. Therefore, work was undertaken by Guth et al. (2017) to autonomize the AHDB variety selection tool. They proposed a voting method that considers all the characteristics available in the AHDB database and assigns a value to them or uses their value from the database, such as in the case of disease resistance, which is based on a 1–9 scale, with 1 being very susceptible and 9 being resistant. Therefore, once a user has entered their site-specific scenario and agronomical factor priorities, the tool will give the most suited varieties in the database. Yang et al. (2024) show that the AHDB variety selection tool has much room for improvement, and it cannot accurately predict cultivar performance at a regional level at present.

Barkley et al. (2010) suggest that lessons should be earned from the world of business in variety selection. They use business portfolio theory to choose several varieties to maximize yield with a reduced level of risk. However, there are limitations, as this will not be applicable to small farm holdings where only one or two varieties of each crop may be grown. Despite this, Sundaramoorthi and Dong (2022) built on this study through the use of an machine learning (ML)-based simulation to predict yield and other characteristics based upon specific farm conditions. They claim that this analytics framework can increase the revenue of an average farmer by \$177,369 through a yield increase of 874.3 kg ha⁻¹ over

597 ha. Similarly, Zhong et al. (2018) used hierarchical ML to predict soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.) yield, which can be used in variety selection decisions. Weather and crop production forecasts are used to predict the yield of various varieties, with a median absolute error of 235 kg ha⁻¹. However, the usefulness of this model in a cool Atlantic climate is unknown, where weather and yield prediction can be more troublesome.

Despite the availability of multiple publicly accessible tools, none have been specifically designed to assist cereal growers worldwide by integrating localized data sources. Given the generally low uptake of such tools, the development of a globally accessible system tailored to the needs of each region could broaden the appeal of the system and ensure sufficient grower adoption to establish the system as a successful solution. This work proposes the development of a novel DSS for cereal variety selection, leveraging region-specific characteristics and grower priorities to generate a ranking of recommended varieties for a given scenario using the simple additive weighting (SAW) method.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section describes the data sources, user input requirements, and the selection process used to identify the most appropriate cereal varieties based upon user-defined priorities. Although this study focuses on winter wheat, the proposed system is designed to accommodate other cereal crops, including barley, spring wheat, and oats.

2.1 | Data sources

To support grower variety selection, governmental bodies and independent research bodies undertake independent variety evaluation trials over several years at a number of sites across the principal cereal crop production areas of many different countries, culminating in the publication of recommended lists of the varieties most suitable for their respective climatic and agricultural conditions (Yang et al., 2024).

These recommended lists systematically assign scores to various varietal characteristics deemed important to grow a successful crop in the region's specific context. While single-factor analyses can be readily conducted across varieties with ease by comparing the scores of each variety for a chosen characteristic, most real-world decisions involve trade-offs across multiple characteristics. This necessitates a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) approach. However, manual execution of MCDM, without a DSS, proves impractical. For this study, the recommended lists serve as the primary dataset. These lists are publicly available and widely used by growers and agronomists, representing multi-location, multi-year trial data.

Core Ideas

- Selecting the right cereal variety is critical for economic and agronomic success.
- An overload of information can make the decision-making process arduous and time-consuming.
- A variety selection decision support system with global usability has been developed.
- Local independent trial results, field location, and grower priorities inform the system.
- Two use cases from Ireland and New Zealand are described.

2.2 | User input

In this study, an end-user is required to provide their location (the county or district in which the field they are choosing the variety for is located) and up to three varietal characteristics in order of importance. These priorities must correspond to the characteristics listed in the recommended lists. In addition to this, for this research, aggregated totals for certain groupings of characteristics, for example, “total disease resistance,” which is a weighted average value from the available disease resistance scores. The end-user also has the option to include previous on-farm grain yields of each variety to incorporate site-specific information and their own previous experiences with certain varieties. Varieties with which a grower lacks experience retain the relative yield values provided in the recommended list.

2.3 | Selection process

Varietal characteristics are reported on differing scales: for example, disease characteristics may be scored on a 1–9 scale where 9 is fully resistant and 1 is fully susceptible, or on a written scale from susceptible to resistant, and yield is scored on a relative scale where the mean of a number of popular varieties is given a score of 100, and other crop characteristics such as straw length, hectoliter weight, and so forth are scored on absolute measurement values. To standardize these heterogeneous data, a SAW scoring method is proposed. The SAW method is an MCDM method that ranks alternatives by summing the products of normalized criteria values and their associated weights. There are four steps in this method: identifying the decision criteria, normalizing the criteria values, assigning weightings to these values, and then aggregating the resulting values of each criterion. Normalization of recommended list scores must occur first to transform the heterogeneous criteria data into comparable

FIGURE 1 Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board (AHDB) winter wheat variety selection tool graphical user interface (AHDB, 2024).

data for scoring and selection purposes. In this system, each characteristic is taken individually and is normalized to a 1–10 scale following a max-min normalization equation, as shown in Equation (1), where x_i is the value of the selected characteristic for a specific variety, x_{\min} is the lowest value of any variety for that characteristic, and x_{\max} is the highest value of any variety for that characteristic:

$$y_i = 1 + 9 \times \left(\frac{x_i - x_{\min}}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}} \right) \quad (1)$$

This results in at least one variety having a score of 1 and at least one variety with a score of 10 for each characteristic. The other varieties will fall within this range. As only three grower priorities are included, this ensures that the highest ranking varieties are selected because of the selected characteristics. While Equation (1) caters for all characteristics where a higher value is desirable, this can also be completed where a lower value is desired (e.g., if a shorter variety is a priority) with Equation (2):

$$y_i = 1 + 9 \times \left(\frac{x_{\max} - x_i}{x_{\max} - x_{\min}} \right) \quad (2)$$

The result of these equations is rounded to the nearest whole number to ensure a clear outcome for the end-user. Once all characteristics are normalized, the SAW method is applied. For this DSS, a rank sum method is used to assign weightings to the selection criteria. Ranking scores are first

TABLE 1 Rank sum method calculation for criterion weighting.

Criterion	Weighting
First priority	5
Second priority	4
Third priority	3
Inherent weighting	1.5

given to the selection criteria, which are the user priorities and fixed (inherent) weightings, as can be seen in Table 1, where 5 is the highest or most important ranking.

The weighting to be applied to each criterion is then calculated with Equation (3), where x_i is the rank value of a selection criterion and $\sum_{j=1}^n x_i$ is sum of all the ranking values for each priority and inherent weighting.

$$y_i = \frac{x_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n x_i} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, where a single priority is chosen, this is given a 0.625 weighting (with weightings of 0.1875 for the two inherent weightings), meaning that it is likely that the variety that scores highest for this characteristic will come out on top. Where two priorities are chosen, the top priority is given a weighting of 0.417 and the second priority 0.333, with two inherent weightings of 0.125 each. Finally, where three priorities are chosen, the top priority is given a weighting of 0.333, the second 0.267, and the third 0.2, with two inherent

weightings of 0.1 each. These weightings ensure that no one priority is dominant while still ensuring the highest priority characteristic has a large influence on the result. For each of these scenarios, the normalized value from the characteristic is multiplied by the weighting (i.e., 0.2 weighting = *2) and totaled to give a final figure. The recommendation is then given that the top variety is chosen by the end-user, subject to availability. A note is also given that if two or more varieties have very close scores, there is likely to be little difference between the varieties, and a variety may be chosen based on a singular characteristic, availability, or the end-user's desired market.

In summary, this SAW method normalizes heterogeneous varietal data, applies priority-based weightings using the rank sum method, and presents ranked variety recommendations based on user-defined criteria and location. Two use cases are presented in the following section. One case study is in an Irish context, where unique climatic conditions, including high annual rainfall and significant disease pressure with distinct disease profiles, make it evident that high-performing varieties from neighboring countries often fail to meet the requirements of Irish growers. Consequently, variety selection systems developed in other countries are inadequate for addressing the specific needs of Irish users. The second use case is in a New Zealand context, emphasizing the global potential and uniqueness of this system.

3 | RESULTS

To illustrate its functionality, scenarios involving the developed winter wheat variety selection tools for Ireland and New Zealand are presented. The two scenarios show that the DSS is designed to be adaptable to any geographical location where recommended variety lists are available, enabling global scalability and utilization.

3.1 | Ireland use case

The Irish Department of Agriculture, Food, and the Marine (DAFM) produces recommended lists each year from a series of trial sites across the country. Varieties are assessed for yield, quality, and agronomic traits, and a variety must show “superior merit” over a 3-year period to be provisionally included on the recommended list and a further year to be fully recommended (DAFM, 2024). Data were downloaded from the DAFM website (DAFM, 2024). These variety listings are widely used by growers and farm advisors. Ireland is chosen as a use case for several distinct factors. Ireland is unique with exceptionally high disease pressure, very high grain yield potential, and challenging harvest weather. These climatic conditions result in huge importance being placed on variety selection to ensure cereal crops are productive. The

recommended lists are also quite simple. They do not provide regional data, and the number of varieties listed is limited, as can be seen in Table 2.

3.1.1 | Regional specifications

Most characteristics are scored on a 1–9 scale in the Irish recommended lists. Every characteristic is normalized for use in this DSS, with a higher value desired in all cases, except for straw height, earliness of ripening, and grain protein, where a higher or lower value may be prioritized by the end-user. In addition to this, for this research, calculated totals for certain groupings of characteristics are calculated using the SAW method of calculating weightings. For example, “total disease resistance,” a weighted average value from the septoria (*Zymoseptoria tritici*) (0.416 weighting), yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. *tritici*) (0.25), powdery mildew (*Blumeria graminis* f. sp. *tritici*) (0.167), and fusarium ear blight (*Fusarium graminearum*) (0.167) resistance characteristic scores, allows for a more general and broad disease resistance score if an end-user is interested in more than one disease. Septoria is included with an increased importance and weighting as it is widely accepted as the most economically destructive winter wheat disease in Northern Europe, and especially Ireland (Kildea et al., 2021; O'Driscoll et al., 2014), while remaining at a level below 0.5 ensures that this one characteristic does not become over-dominant. Total straw quality consists of straw breakdown resistance and resistance to lodging, with both characteristics having a 0.5 weighting. Hectoliter weight and 1000-grain weight (TGW) also have a 0.5 weighting each for the total grain quality grouping. Average grain yield considers both the recommended list relative yield and the inputted on-farm yield. The list of possible priorities that a grower may choose from is presented in Table 3.

Once the normalization process has taken place, as shown in Table 4, the application of the weightings, depending on grower priorities, occurs. In addition to the one, two, or three end-user-chosen priorities, two inherent weightings are included in the final selection process and ranking.

An inherent weighting is given to septoria or yellow rust, depending on the location of the field. The southern half of Ireland is relatively warmer than the northern half, and the entire island has a high level of rainfall (Walsh, 2012). Therefore, the south of Ireland has relatively higher septoria pressure due to its warmer and more humid climate (Palmer & Skinner, 2002), while the north of the country has relatively higher yellow rust pressure due to cooler, moist weather (Chen et al., 2014), which gives rise to these inherent weightings, which are included regardless of the user's priorities. Sprouting is also given an inherent weighting as this is an important characteristic for all of Ireland due to the high

TABLE 2 Agronomic and quality characteristics for feed winter wheat varieties adapted from the Irish Department of Agriculture, Food, and the Marine (DAFM) recommended list.

Variety	Graham	KWS Dawsum	Spearhead	Torp	Champion ^a	Fitzroy ^a
Relative yield	102	98	104	105	107	102
Straw height (cm)	75	72	76	77	74	76
Resistance to lodging	6	7	5	7	(5)	(7)
Straw breakdown	5	7	6	6	(6)	(7)
Earliness of ripening	7	6	6	5	(6)	(4)
Resistance to						
Mildew	8	8	8	5	(8)	(8)
Septoria spp.	5	4	5	6	(6)	(7)
Yellow rust	5	8	6	4	(7)	(8)
Fusarium ear blight	5	(7)	(5)	4	(6)	(5)
Sprouting	6	8	4	6	(5)	(7)
Quality						
Grain protein (%)	10.4	9.9	10.0	10.1	10.1	10.0
Hagberg falling number	343	405	164	241	289	342
TGW (g)	51.5	47.5	51.8	49.9	50.2	53.5
Hectolitre weight (kg hL ⁻¹)	76.8	78.6	75.9	74.7	75.6	76.7
Year first listed	2020	2023	2022	2018	2025	2025

Note: Data in brackets refer to characteristics that have been developed from a limited number of trial years.

Abbreviations: TGW, 1000-grain weight.

^aProvisionally recommended varieties.

TABLE 3 Priority options for end-users.

Possible end-user priorities	Possible end-user priorities
Average grain yield	Grain protein % (high or low preference)
Listed grain yield	Sprouting resistance
On-farm grain yield	Total straw quality
Total disease resistance	Lodging resistance ^b
Septoria resistance	Straw breakdown resistance ^b
Yellow/stripe rust resistance	Straw strength ^a
Powdery mildew resistance	Hectoliter weight
Fusarium ear blight resistance	1000-grain weight
Leaf rust resistance ^a	Total grain quality
Hagberg falling number	Screenings ^a
Plant density ^a	Straw height (tall or short preference)
Earliness of ripening (early or late preference)	

^aNew Zealand use case priority option only.

^bIrish use case priority option only.

likelihood of precipitation and humid weather at harvest (Vetch et al., 2019).

3.1.2 | Results

Table 5 demonstrates an example output generated by the proposed system, where the weighting of each characteristic, the

TABLE 4 The normalization of Irish winter wheat yield values.

Variety	Relative yield	Normalized value
Graham	102	5
KWS Dawsum	98	1
Spearhead	104	7
Torp	105	8
Champion	107	10
Fitzroy	102	5

weighted value from each characteristic, and the total value of each variety are illustrated. In this scenario, yield is the top priority of the end-user, followed by hectoliter weight, and third, TGW. The table displays the assigned weightings for each column, followed by the weighted values of each variety for the respective characteristics. This example is for a field in the south of Ireland, as reflected by the inherent weighting for septoria resistance, while the weighting for yellow rust resistance is 0 due to its reduced importance in this region. An inherent weighting for sprouting resistance is also included. The total values for each variety are calculated and presented in the rightmost column, where varieties are ranked from best to worst based on their overall performance.

The results indicate that Fitzroy, with a total score of 70.67, is the most suitable variety for this scenario, followed by Champion with 61.31. KWS Dawsum performs the worst, with a total score of 43.03. This variety should not be chosen

TABLE 5 An example of the weightings and output of the Irish winter wheat variety selection system.

Characteristic	Yield	Hectoliter weight	TGW	Septoria resistance	Yellow rust resistance	Sprouting resistance	Total
Weighting	0.333	0.267	0.2	0.1	0	0.1	1
Fitzroy	16.65	16.02	20	10	0	8	70.67
Champion	33.3	8.01	10	7	0	3	61.31
Graham	16.65	16.02	14	4	0	6	56.67
Spearhead	23.31	10.68	14	4	0	1	52.99
Torp	26.64	2.67	10	7	0	6	52.31
KWS Dawsum	3.33	26.7	2	1	0	10	43.03

Abbreviation: TGW, 1000-grain weight.

by this grower in this region as it is unsuitable unless no other options are available or there is a specific market demand for this variety. Although Champion has the highest weighted value for the top priority, yield (33.3), Fitzroy, even with a lower yield value (16.65), surpasses Champion due to its superior rankings in the second and third priorities, as well as the contributions from the inherent weightings. The weighted values presented in the table provide a clear breakdown of the areas in which each variety excels or underperforms relative to specific characteristics given the importance of each priority. This transparency allows growers to make informed decisions, understanding the trade-offs between characteristics and selecting a variety that best aligns with their priorities and site-specific conditions.

3.2 | New Zealand use case

In New Zealand, independent cereal variety trials are conducted by Foundation for Arable Research, which then produces an annual cultivar evaluation booklet containing lists of recommended varieties (FAR, 2023). These lists contain results from the previous year's harvest, 4-year adjusted mean yields, and other agronomic data from trials conducted throughout New Zealand. With a different climate and soil than Ireland, but with a version of recommended variety listings, it demonstrates the possibility of the system to work in any location where recommended lists are available. The New Zealand variety listings are also structured differently. They possess regional yield and grain quality data in addition to irrigated and dryland yield data. Data are also presented for different markets, the feed/biscuit market, and the milling market. Finally, a number of characteristics are ranked categorically, for example, from short to tall for straw height, emphasizing the wide range of possibilities for the system.

3.2.1 | Regional differences

Before a grower can use the system in a New Zealand context, first they must select the market they wish to grow

wheat for, whether that be feed/biscuit or milling. They must also select their region and whether the crop will be irrigated or not. These selections inform the system as to what varieties and characteristic scores are to be considered. Most characteristics are scored on categorical scales in the New Zealand recommended lists. Diseases are scored on a seven-point list from susceptible to resistant, straw strength on a five-point scale from weak to stiff, straw height on a five-point scale from short to tall, earliness of ripeness on a five-point scale from early to late, and sprouting resistance on a six-point scale from very low to high. Every characteristic is first equated to a numeric scale, for example, with "susceptible" equaling 1, and "resistant" equaling 7. For sprouting resistance, "very low" equates to a score of 1 and "high" to a score of 6 due to the desire to have a variety to have low susceptibility to sprouting. Other characteristics are scored based on absolute measurement values as shown in Table 6.

The characteristics are then normalized. A high score is desired for most characteristics, except for straw height, earliness of ripeness, and grain protein %, where a higher or lower value may be prioritized by the end-user, and screenings, where a lower value is prioritized. Grouped characteristics are also available here. "total disease resistance" is a weighted average value from the septoria (0.2 weighting), stripe rust (0.2), leaf rust (*Puccinia triticina*) (0.2), powdery mildew (0.2), and fusarium ear blight (0.2) resistance characteristic scores. The remaining groupings each have two characteristics included, with a 0.5 weighting applied to each one. Total straw quality consists of straw strength and straw height. A tall or short crop can be chosen as the desired trait. Hectoliter weight and TGW are considered for the total grain quality grouping, while average grain yield consists of the listed recommended list relative yield and the inputted on-farm yield. The list of possible priorities that a New Zealand grower may choose from is presented in Table 3.

In the selection process, two inherent weightings are given. The first is to septoria resistance, as septoria is a major wheat disease in New Zealand, especially in autumn-sown crops (Stewart et al., 2014). The second is given to sprouting

TABLE 6 Select agronomic and quality characteristics for canterbury feed and biscuit autumn-sown wheat varieties adapted from the New Zealand Foundation for Arable Research (FAR) recommended list.

Variety	TGW (g)	Hectoliter weight (kg hL ⁻¹)	Grain protein (%)	Screenings (%)
Firelight	48	73	9.8	0.8
Firefly	54	74	10.4	0.3
Graham	51	76	10.1	0.5
Ignite	46	75	10.6	0.5
Kerrin	46	74	9.7	1.5
Kinetic	52	76	9.8	0.5
Reflection	46	74	9.9	1.1
Starfire	44	75	10.6	0.8
SY Defiant	52	78	9.8	0.5
Voltron	46	76	10.1	0.6
Whopper	48	75	10.2	0.5
CRWT267	49	70	10.5	0.6
CRWT268	45	74	10.2	1.1
KFW2102	51	76	10.0	0.4
KFW2201	52	76	9.8	0.5

Abbreviation: TGW, 1000-grain weight.

TABLE 7 An example of the weightings and output of the New Zealand autumn-sown wheat variety selection system.

Characteristic	Yield	Hectoliter weight	TGW	Septoria resistance	Sprouting resistance	Total
Weighting	0.333	0.267	0.2	0.1	0.1	1
SY Defiant	23.31	26.7	18	10	10	88.01
KFW2201	33.3	21.36	16	7	4	81.66
Kinetic	23.31	21.36	16	4	7	71.67
KFW2102	23.31	21.36	15	7	4	70.67
Firefly	19.98	16.02	16	10	4	66
Graham	16.65	21.36	15	4	7	64.01
CRWT268	19.98	16.02	8	7	7	58
Voltron	16.65	21.36	11	1	7	57.01
Whopper	16.65	18.69	12	4	4	55.34
Reflection	16.65	16.02	9	4	7	52.67
Firelight	19.98	10.68	9	7	1	47.66
Ignite	9.99	18.69	10	1	4	43.68
Kerrin	9.99	16.02	9	1	4	40.01
Starfire	3.33	18.69	8	1	4	35.02
CRWT267	16.65	2.67	7	7	1	34.32

Abbreviation: TGW, 1000-grain weight.

resistance as conditions conducive to pre-harvest sprouting are common in the maritime climate.

3.2.2 | Results

Table 7 demonstrates an example output of the New Zealand system where a grower (located in Canterbury) wishes to grow

a feed/biscuit wheat. The field will also be irrigated. In this scenario, yield is the top priority of the end-user, followed by hectoliter weight and TGW.

In the ranking table, SY Defiant achieved the highest score of 88.01, making it the most appropriate variety for this scenario. This was followed by KFW2201, with a total score of 81.66. Conversely, CRWT267 recorded the lowest performance, with a total score of 34.32. KFW2201 has the highest

weighted value for the top priority, yield (33.3); however, SY Defiant surpasses it due to its higher performance in the other priorities, as well as the inherent weightings, despite a lower score for yield. With a large number of varieties on the recommended list, the breakdown of the weighted value in the table allows growers to discern the differences between varieties when the total values are similar.

4 | DISCUSSION

A system has been proposed to recommend an appropriate cereal variety to an arable grower based upon official recommended lists. It has been created to ensure that a grower can choose the most suitable variety according to their priorities and their field's location. The system is straightforward, with only one dataset being considered, and that dataset being a publicly available document.

The system uses a SAW method, including a max-min normalization system, to ensure that each characteristic is considered equally, whether a high or low value is desirable. The normalization of the characteristics also ensures that there is adequate differentiation between the varieties for each characteristic. While this means that two varieties that have similar values may have substantially different normalized values, this is desirable to ensure that the most appropriate result for the end-user's priorities is produced. Additional trait groups, such as total disease resistance or total straw quality, give an end-user an opportunity to include more traits in the model or to recommend a variety that is adequate across a broad basis. The inclusion of a grower's priorities and the availability of these additional trait groups provide an improvement on current variety selection systems. Detlefsen and Jensen (2004) provide a system where the user can sort, rank, and filter the variety listing. However, it does not allow for more than one priority to be included or for variety of traits to be grouped. Similarly, the inclusion of location and subsequent inherent geographical characteristics ensures that recommendations are made with regional differences in the described system but not in the Danish system. However, the AHDB (2024) variety selection tool does provide regional data and rankings.

The given scenarios emphasize the importance and scope of this system. In the Irish scenario, it is likely that a grower operating without the help of the DSS would choose Champion as their variety as it has a higher relative yield than the other varieties and the grower's top priority is yield. However, this system considers a grower's second and third priorities and their location. In this case, the system recommends Fitzroy. Despite a much lower relative yield, it performs well on the grower's second and third priorities, allowing it to overtake Champion. Without using this system, a crop of Champion may be infected by septoria, and the resulting grain may be

of low quality due to lower TGW and hectoliter weight trait values. Even if this results in a slightly higher yield, Fitzroy will be a more satisfactory outcome for the end-user. The New Zealand use case portrays a similar scenario. SY Defiant is the top-ranked variety despite trailing KFW2201 on the top priority of yield by 42.86%, 23.31–33.3. The second and third priorities and the inherent weightings show the balance of the SAW method and the DSS, with one characteristic score unable to dominate and disrupt the decision-making process, ensuring that the chosen variety will be satisfactory across all grower priorities.

The system is also very useful when considering varieties that are new to the market. If a grower has not already grown a certain variety, and their peers have little or no knowledge of a variety, the recommended lists are the only independent source of information for the farmer. This system can help growers to compare new and established varieties. As can be seen in the New Zealand use case, the DSS is very beneficial when there are many varieties to consider. The system efficiently ranks the varieties, and the grower can view why each variety performs well or badly when the priorities and weightings are applied. While larger growers may choose multiple varieties to plant to spread risk, small-scale growers will typically plant one variety of a crop. Some current variety selection DSSs only cater for large-scale growers where multiple varieties are planted (Barkley et al., 2010; Sundaramoorthi & Dong, 2022). With 63.8% of EU farms under 5 ha in size and 92.5% under 50 ha (Eurostat, 2020), it is critical that a DSS will support all farms. The described system has the potential to support both small-scale growers wishing to plant one variety and large-scale growers who wish to plant more than one variety.

The described use cases demonstrate how the developed system works with a recommended list from Ireland or New Zealand. This emphasizes the scope of the system; it can be adapted and modified for any country with published independent recommended lists, such as the United Kingdom (AHDB, 2025), Brazil (CBPTT, 2024), Canada (Atlantic Grains Council, 2025), and Germany (Federal Plant Variety Office, 2025). This must be achieved to fully realize the potential of the system. Local knowledge would be beneficial to ensure that any local factors to be accounted for via a field's location are captured to maximize accuracy, such as the inherent septoria, yellow rust, and sprouting weightings included in the Irish version of this DSS. The system may also be adapted for other cereal and non-cereal crops where recommended lists are available. In the Irish use case, recommended lists are a summary of independent field trial results and do not provide a regional breakdown of results, and there are no regional differences given. While the system takes this into account with the inherent geographical traits, improvements could be made with the release of independent trial data from individual trial sites across Ireland. This would allow for

region-specific recommendations to be given by the system, building grower trust that the recommendations are appropriate for their farm. This is already available in some national recommended lists, such as those of the United Kingdom and New Zealand (AHDB, 2025; FAR, 2023). In the New Zealand use case, the system only considers data from irrigated Canterbury, ensuring that trial data that is of less relevance are not included. The system therefore recommends a variety based on more local and relevant data.

While the described system has been created, future work will consider improving the user-friendliness and accessibility of the system. This will involve the creation of a web app and smartphone application to ensure access to the system is simple and help to ensure that grower uptake is improved compared to the low uptake of similar DSSs (McCown et al., 2002; McGregor & Thornton, 1990; Thysen, 2007). The input page will involve dropdown boxes for the user's priorities and field location. Graphical visualization of the ranked results will be considered to ensure the user is clear on the recommendations given, similar to the UK DSS (AHDB, 2024). Validation of the given recommendations must also occur in two ways. First, growers will be consulted and asked what varieties they have planted. They will then be asked to use the system, and the result will be recorded. If the result is different from the grower's choice, they will be asked which variety they would now plant and why. This will result in a greater understanding of farmer willingness to adopt this technology and provide feedback on the accuracy of the system. Second, on-farm field trials should be undertaken by several growers. This would consist of planting their own variety and the system's chosen variety to assess the economic and agronomic effectiveness of using the system.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

The selection of a cereal crop variety is a critical decision for growers, one that must be made prior to the growing season and is influenced by numerous agronomic and site-specific factors. Independent variety trials, their subsequent results, and recommended lists are valuable resources to support this decision-making process. However, the complexity of MCDM often poses a challenge for growers. This work proposes a novel system designed to address the variety selection problem. Through the integration of site-specific factors that can have agronomic importance and a grower's crop priorities, the system enables the scoring and ranking of key varietal characteristics that are critical to fulfilling the unique priorities and needs of each field a grower plans to plant through the use of the SAW method.

This system contains limitations due to the lack of availability of local independent trial results informing official recommended variety listings. The availability of trial data

with a high level of granularity would help to address this limitation and improve the site-specific aspects of this system. Future work will focus on validating and enhancing the system using in-field trial results and regional trial results to generate more site-specific recommendations and therefore more tailored and actionable guidance for growers. This approach represents a significant step toward optimizing cereal variety selection, ultimately improving agricultural productivity and sustainability in a global context.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conor J. Kehoe: Conceptualization; investigation; methodology; writing—original draft; writing—review and editing. **Gary D. Gillespie:** Investigation; methodology; writing—review and editing. **Kevin P. McDonnell:** Conceptualization; funding acquisition; supervision; writing—review and editing.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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